

The water vibrations.

(by Neri Roberto. It is part of the research done for the study of Mattei remedies)

How many times have we heard about informed water, memory of water, waters of Light, vibrational waters.

If we could create an instrument capable of measuring any vibrations of water perhaps we could try to understand the meaning of these statements.

The aim of this work is to build a device capable of detecting any vibrations in the water so as to be able to characterize and identify them.

For years I have tried to record, using coils and a series of amplifiers, the electromagnetic field generated by water with disappointing results. The background noise was always very high compared to the signals I wanted to measure even in shielded containers. So after seeing the work of Daniele Gullà who uses a hyperspectral camera patented by him to analyze the vibrations of things (biological and otherwise), I also decided to move on to mechanical vibrations which are probably the origin of the electromagnetic field we are looking for.

The idea therefore is to use instead of a camera, which must manage a high number of pixels, a single sensor which can be much larger than a pixel of a camera and therefore more sensitive. This also allows us to sample the analog signal faster and consequently have a greater bandwidth. If we then use a laser that emits a coherent light beam, we can think of measuring the variations in intensity of the interference figure that is created between the laser beam reflected by the surface of the transparent container and the one that passes through the water to be analyzed .

We therefore create a LASER interferometer in a dark room composed of a small box lined inside with spongy material that absorbs external vibrations.

The light source is a LASER diode that emits a beam at 650nm (red) while the sensor is a photodiode that has its maximum sensitivity at the same frequency.

The sensor will be connected to a transimpedance operational amplifier which amplifies the signal 1,000,000 times with a frequency response of 0 to 14 KHz.

Let's see the dark room interferometer without the cover:

The interferometer is a device capable of separating a single ray of coherent light (LASER) into two rays which, after having traveled different optical paths, recombine, forming an interference pattern, observable on a screen.

In optics, the property of an electromagnetic wave to maintain a certain phase relationship with itself during its propagation is called coherence (or phase coherence).

The interferometer output will then be connected to an audio/USB interface managed by a personal computer.

For real-time data analysis and recording we use a spectral analysis program.

The spectrum analyzer shows us the frequency in Hz on the horizontal axis while on the vertical axis we have the time.

A screen shows us 8 minutes of recording.

The first image is what we see on the screen when we analyze tap water. The golden yellow horizontal lines correspond to the opening of the box (darkroom) to reposition in this case the same tap water.

The strong signal (larger amplitude) corresponds to a more light color.

There are NO visible vibrations.

In December 2015 (8 years ago) I placed a bottle of Pejo water for a week in the pentagonal tower of the Rocchetta castle where Count Mattei stored his remedies (there are still the appropriate shelves on the walls).

These are the results as of today 04/07/2023

Tap water we use as control at the top and Pejo water at the bottom:

You can see a remarkable activity of the water that was a week 8 years ago in the pentagonal tower compared to the tap water.

At this point we compare the water of the tower with the waters of the springs that we find near the castle.

This is torre2015 on Sterpi (the water from the spring under Monte Vigese)

The behavior of the 2 waters is very similar at 9.41pm.

Let's see in the morning. The sun is rising, it's 5:28

Sterpi on torre2015:

It seems that Torre is much more active than the night before while Sterpi are still the same

. Let's now analyze the water from another spring on Montovolo (La Faggia spring) on the water of the Sterpi recording dated 15/07/2023

The water from the La Faggia spring does NOT vibrate like that of the Sterpi

Let us now analyze some phytotherapeutic preparations currently on the market produced by Mr. Vincenzo Castellano

In 2020 I asked the manufacturer to send me, with the samples, also a bottle of untreated water identified by him as distilled water.

To take the measurements we transfer the contents of the dark glass bottles supplied into the transparent plastic containers:

Electrovis 1 on distilled water (control) (registered July 22, 2023)

You can clearly see that the treatment done a couple of years ago is still effective. Note that in the lower part, untreated distilled water has no vibration. Electrovis4 su electrovis2:

Note the component at 12.48HZ at -17db one of the highest values measured at the moment.

At this point, to verify the interferometer, I provide 5 cc of tower water, taken from the sample we analyzed in the previous slides, to Daniene Gullà who will take the measurements with a machine he created which uses a different technology from mine. Below are the results:

On the left the values recorded by Gullà and on the right those of the interferometer (the morning results are in blue and the evening results are in red).

The results, considering the frequencies and not the amplitudes which vary continuously, are comparable and this comforts me a lot.

Let us now analyze a water that is offered to the faithful displayed on a shelf next to the House of Mary in the basilica of Loreto.

The basilica is one of the main places of veneration of Mary and among the most important and visited Marian sanctuaries.

Tap water we use as a control on Loreto water (0-100Hz):

The differences are evident: we have a very high general activity in Loreto water compared to tap water and characteristic peaks at levels even 40 db higher (10,000 times greater).

This is Loreto water from 0 to 100Hz

(10 Sep 2023) Also in our territory we have a Marian cult site, the Sanctuary of the Blessed Virgin of Montovolo. Prendiamo 2 contenitori di acqua dal rubinetto della canonica uno lo mettiamo in macchina fuori dalla chiesa e uno ai piedi della statua della madonna nell'abside della chiesa nei giorni della festa. Dopo 2 giorni questi sono i risultati

In alto l'acqua ai piedi della madonna in basso quella sul sedile dell'auto

Even the water that was in the car (in fact a few meters from the church) vibrates, less but it vibrates. If we increase the spectrum we see

MMovolo on Movolo from 0 to 200Hz (just taken).

The spectral content of the one at the top (Madonna di Montovolo) is much greater than the one at the bottom.

Let's now compare the Loreto waters on MMOVolo.

The water of the MMOVolo is slightly less strong but the frequencies are the same.

The audio recording of Loreto2 follows, note the difference between the first part of the signal (Loreto water) and the second (tap water)

Here you can see a big difference between the energy of Loreto water (the left part) compared to tap water (right part).

Conclusions:

We therefore now have the opportunity to see whether water vibrates or not (like tap water) and also whether it vibrates with a lot or little intensity.

We have seen that the amplitudes are not constant and change even during a recording of a few minutes and still seem to depend on the moment in which they are taken (morning or evening).

The frequencies, however, seem quite stable over time and this would allow us to identify and therefore recognize one water from another.

We are just at the beginning, the next step will be to try to put information into the water and analyze the results.

Now we can do this with the interferometer.

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